

IMPROVED MODEL OF PREPARATION OF STUDENTS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES ON THE BASIS OF CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM

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Abstract: *When preparing students for professional activity, the development of a methodological model of training in a credit-modular system, its components, is considered. In particular, the purpose, content, forms, methods and techniques of teaching are presented on a systematic basis. Most importantly, the importance of the credit-modular system in education is described in detail. The article presents an improved model of teaching materials in a credit-modular system. This model covers the entire system. A separate feature is that this model also describes the goals and objectives of learning in a credit-modular system. The improved model of preparing students for professional activity takes into account the factors of the professional-pedagogical approach.*

Keywords: *credit module, methodology, model, system approach, projects, e-book, didactics, curriculum, interdisciplinary communication, pedagogical technology.*

Preparing future teachers on Technology for professional activities is a complex process. In the implementation of this process, an important role is played by improving the model of the educational process. In the pedagogical and scientific literature there are different approaches and definitions given by pedagogical scientists in relation to the concept of "model of preparation of future specialists for professional activity". Many authors emphasized the understanding of features that reflect the model of the preparation of future specialists for professional activity, the main factors of the object under study as an integrated image of the professional activity of a particular field specialist. One of the scientists on Pedagogy in Uzbekiston N.A.Muslimov noted that the model of preparation of future specialists for innovative professional activity consists of the following three components.

1. Types of activities that arise on the basis of features inherent in the new social stage.

2. Types of activities in which the professional requirements are clearly indicated.

3. The socio-political structure of the state, as well as the types of activities that are organized according to the essence of its spiritual and moral system.

The model of preparation of future specialists for innovative professional activity is a template that provides a successful solution to the problematic situations that arise in professional activity, describes certain pedagogical qualities and reflects the independent acquisition of knowledge and self – development of the owner of the profession.

Based on the results of the research, the model of preparation of future specialists for innovative professional activity was determined-the logical structure of the methodology of obtaining knowledge and formation of skills using the credit-module system in the teaching of specialty subjects, which should be mastered in the audience training and independent education in the achievement of the expert level.

On the basis of the credit-module system, the improved model of preparation of students for professional activity consists of "goal", "organizational", "content", "result" components, all components are explained below.

On the basis of the credit-module system, the improved model components of the preparation of students for professional activities are explained as follows:

Goal component

Qualification requirements: scientific-research, design-construction, production, organizational-management, use, service, types of pedagogical activity are provided for the preparation of teachers of future technology science.

Model Objective: This is an expression from teaching future technology science teachers on the basis of improving the methodology of using credit-module system in their professional activities.

Organizational component

On the basis of the objective of improving the methodology of using the credit-module system in the professional activity of future teachers on Technology in the model, on the basis of educational-methodical and didactic

provision of future teachers on Technology, on the basis of innovative approaches, software educational tools and principles, didactic, organizational and methodological features were studied.

Educational-methodical and didactic provision-the purposeful and effective use of materials prepared in the curriculum of the direction of technological education on the subjects (textbooks, manuals, methodical manuals, educational-methodical complexes).

Software tools - on subjects in the curriculum of the specialty of technological education (E-textbook, electronic manual, electronic educational-methodological complexes, 3D animations prepared on topics that are not possible to impress students, virtual laboratories prepared on laboratory subjects that do not have a material and technical base, audio and visual materials for the purpose of improving the educational opportunities of students independently) virtual reality design, mathematical modeling, features of virtual reality, developed on the basis of the basic principles of didactics.

Approaches - in the preparation of students of the specialty of technological education for innovative professional activity were carried out on the basis of approaches in the use of the credit-module system (logical, evristic, integrative, critical, creative, innovative).

Transparent education ECTS credit-module system requires students to convey all the information relevant to their learning processes in a predictable, understandable, complete and transparent manner. In this case, the university will have to provide students with complete and transparent information in advance about what subjects they need to master during their entire study, the expected reading results from them, what methods and standards the students will be tested on. The increase in the number of HEIs, the penetration of selection sciences into educational programs also further exacerbates the need for transparency in education. Because in order for the student to literally exercise his or her right of choice, he or she must have entire preliminary knowledge of the program and the subjects in it. The student can not exercise his / her right of choice only if he / she knows the name of the faculty or the name of the subject.

The provision of educational intercession in ECTS credit – module system is reflected in the following rules:

Each subject in the curriculum is reflected in a certain amount of credits. That is, given the fact that each loan represents an average 25-30 hour reading

load, the student will have a preliminary knowledge of the reading load of this course, depending on the amount of credits distributed to a particular subject.

Each university at the beginning of the academic year develops its own catalogue of programs on educational programs and presents it to students. The program catalog can be placed on the HEI web page or provided to students in another way.

Each course in the curriculum is coded with its own reflection of certain information. In the curriculum, each course is coded in such a way that it is level, interrelated with other course, choice or compulsory subject and contains similar information, and this is explained to the students about the content of the codes. On the basis of the above, the organization of classes in the specialty of "technological education", the application of visual techniques have been identified in scientific research, in particular, it has a positive impact on the formation of professional knowledge, skills and qualifications of future teachers as a result of virtual demonstration of work activity.

In conclusion, it is of particular importance that on the basis of this methodology it is aimed at improving the use of credit-module system in the preparation of future teachers of Technology subject.

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